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Paper

Title: Analysis of legal tools which allow for new sustainable approaches to residential buildings and opinion on foreseeable legislative action: An exploratory study of legal frameworks at the European level

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Section 1. Introduction.

This paper explains and critically analyses *Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on energy performance of buildings* (Energy Performance of Buildings Directive – EPBD) by breaking it down into different crucial aspects and examining the provisions in the light of detailed evidence for the development of certain arguments. To expand on the topic of the energy performance of the buildings, different interpretations of the laws and facts form the foundation for the explanation of the Directive. Achieving a reduction in the energy consumption of the buildings, is, therefore, the epicentre of all the policies, conventions and administrative laws since building stock accounts for more than 40% of final energy consumption¹. Consequently, a list of arguments and converging relations between different complicated points help us understand how the objectives for net-zero-energy buildings get translated into real-time national laws, regulations and administrative procedures, starting from the founding Treaties that exist with regards to the interests of the Communities. The paper verifies whether the provisions set in the Directive are fully transposed by the Member States or not and to what extent does the Commission adopt the measures to update the objectives in order to set new targets for the next decade. Since the existing buildings need renovations that span for prolonged periods the critical analysis of the Directive, therefore, identifies key shreds of evidence that point to how the solution can be constituted with regards to the existing building stock. It reflects on the next question which is whether the Member States have been effective to implement the measures or what are the findings that lead to. And in light of the experience gained because of the provisions in different directives over a period of time, how does *Regulation (EU) 2017/1369* catalyse the energy-labelling of the products supporting energy-efficiency. The paper is split into different sections wherein the initial two sections give fuller account and versions of the founding Treaties, Directives and Regulations, thus analysing, absorbing and interpreting the legal literature. While sections four and five are based on case law and evaluations of legal frameworks at the international, European, national and regional levels. Thus leaving the evidence-based findings for the conclusion.

¹ DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU.

Section 2. Crucial aspects and importance of Treaty of Rome (European Economic Community – EEC Treaty) and Treaty of Maastricht (The Treaty on European Union - TEU) concerning environmental problems and sustainability.

“Treaty of Rome” or “European Economic Community Treaty” (‘EEC’), which got amended many times to become what it is today, the “Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union” (‘TFEU’), focused on bringing common market, aligned economic policies and principles of UN Charter, improving the standard of living and joint policies on environmental, regional, social and industrial levels between six European countries². The principles laid out in ‘EEC’, clearly defines the functioning of the Union and the boundaries of and different alignments for its competencies. *Article 4* of ‘TFEU’ under “Categories and Areas of Union Competence” establishes the shared role between the Union and the Member States, for the first time, in the areas of ‘environment and energy’³. The primary law that provides the legal context to European Union (EU) institutions, within which they structure policies and laws, is based on the founding treaties viz. ‘TFEU’ and ‘TEU’⁴. *Article 191* of ‘TFEU’ (primary law) is important as it aims to set out the framework for the European Union’s policies based on sustainability, environmental problems and energy efficiency on the account of available scientific and technical data⁵. It addresses within the respective spheres of competencies of the Union and the Member States⁶.

Objectives set in ‘TFEU’ for ‘environment’ under *Article 191* (primary law) dictate the Union and the Member States to devise the policies and framework in the direction of sustainability and environmental protection broadly. What needs to be understood concerning the provisions under ‘TFEU’ is, ways to achieve the goals and who is responsible to what extent. And whether the laws (secondary laws) that result from these policies are fulfilling the objectives.

² European Union, 2022. *Summaries of EU Legislation*. Retrieved from [EUR-Lex - 114530 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eur-lex.do?uri=CELEX:32022R0001:EN:EUR-Lex). Accessed on 25th February 2022.

³ Consolidated Version of The Treaty On The Functioning Of The European Union (‘TFEU’), 2020, Title I, Categories and Areas of Union Competence, Article 4, p.46.

⁴ European Union (n 1).

⁵ Consolidated Version of The Treaty On The Functioning Of The European Union (‘TFEU’), 2020, Title XX, Environment, Article 191, p. 126-127.

⁶ *ibid* p. 127.

Article 288 of ‘TFEU’, under ‘Legal Acts of the Union’, sets out the meanings of ‘Regulations’, ‘Directives’, ‘Decisions’, ‘Recommendations’ and ‘Opinions’, forming the base for secondary law⁷. *Article 288* of ‘TFEU’, therefore, equips the Union and the Member States to pass legislative acts (secondary law) on sustainability, environment and energy efficiency. Authorizing the Union and the Member States to take their positions on legal tools to achieve the defined goals and harmonize with *Article 191* of ‘TFEU’ (primary law).

It is also necessary to understand how different treaties address the priorities of sustainability and environmental damages in conjunction with ‘TFEU’. This is where the founding “Treaty on European Union” plays a pivotal role as well. The pioneering “Treaty of Maastricht”, today officially known as “Treaty on European Union” (‘TEU’)⁸, “marks a new stage in the process of creating an ever closer union among the peoples of Europe, in which decisions are taken as closely as possible to the citizen.”⁹ ‘TEU’ established the pillars of the Union and the Member States (viz. the European Parliament, Commission, Court of Justice and European Central Bank) and elucidated objectives that would embolden “the provisions of the Treaties establishing the European Communities”¹⁰. *Article 130r* of ‘TEU’ not only sets out the framework and objectives for the environment at all levels that supersede with ‘TFEU’ but also states that the Union and the Member States should take positions on legal tools in accordance with *Article 288* of ‘TFEU’, under ‘Point 4’¹¹. Additionally, *Article 3b* of ‘TEU’ brings one of the major institutional changes by stating the principle of subsidiarity¹². This affects the scope of environment-related directives and policies too, as the EU will take action rather than the Member States if objectives can be better achieved at the EU level¹³.

With the help of teleological and systematic interpretations of the founding Treaties relevant to sustainability, the extent of the legal provisions becomes evident.

⁷ Consolidated Version of The Treaty On The Functioning Of The European Union (‘TFEU’), 2020, Article 288, p. 171-172.

⁸ European Union, 2022. *Summaries of EU Legislation*. Retrieved from [EUR-Lex - 114530 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eur-lex.do?uri=EN:EUR-Lex:europa.eu). Accessed on 26th February 2022.

⁹ Treaty on European Union (92/C 191/01), 1992, Title I, Common Provisions, Article A, p. 4.

¹⁰ *ibid* Article E, p. 4.

¹¹ *ibid* Title XVI, Environment, Article 130r, Point 4, p.29.

¹² *ibid* Article 3b, p.6

¹³ *ibid* Article 3b, p.6.

Section 3. Critically analysing Directive 2010/31/EU, Regulation (EU) 2017/1369 and progress on energy performance of buildings.

Directive 2010/31/EU, having regard to ‘TFEU’ (also relating to *Article 191* and *Article 288*)¹⁴ and *Article 194(2)* in particular¹⁵, on the energy performance of buildings (‘EPBD’) stipulates that energy trilemma is of prime importance and the global energy market in the long-term is thus influenced by management of energy security, environmental sustainability and energy equity¹⁶. Commission Communication set objectives, in ‘Action plan of energy efficiency: realising the potential’, of achieving 20% energy efficiency target for 2020 and commitment of meeting required CO₂ emissions for 2020, in 2007, making the binding target of energy efficiency in building sector very crucial¹⁷. This turned out to be the base for the *Directive 2010/31/EU* that amended provisions in *Directive 2002/91/EC*¹⁸ and reaffirmed *Directive 2009/28/EC*¹⁹ back in 2010. It is critical to understand that the EU’s final energy consumption in 2020 eventually was 5.4% below the 2020 energy target that was set in *Directive 2010/31/EU* and 7.2% above the 2030 target²⁰. Binding targets, measures, objectives and promotion of energy efficiency in the context of building stock, therefore, worked in the light of gaining experience and application of *Directive 2010/31/EU*. Therefore, before dissecting the *Directive 2010/31/EU* into pivotal details supported by shreds of evidence, it is fundamentally necessary to highlight the progress and arguments concerning clean energy technology.

Energy balance calculations of the building envelope set down the need for absolute energy demands. It includes heating and domestic hot water energy demands. The resulting useful energy is considered to calculate the final, total and primary energy demands by taking into account the grid distribution, storage and generation efficiencies²¹. Finally, the efficiencies of heat pumps, PV systems, gas-boilers, other

¹⁴ Consolidated Version of The Treaty On The Functioning Of The European Union (‘TFEU’), 2020.

¹⁵ DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings, p.1.

¹⁶ *ibid* Point 4, p.1.

¹⁷ *ibid* Point 5, p.1.

¹⁸ *ibid* Point 1, p.1.

¹⁹ *ibid* Point 6, p.2.

²⁰ Eurostat, European Union, 2022. *Energy Efficiency Statistics*. Retrieved from [Glossary: Eurostat - Statistics Explained \(europa.eu\)](#). Accessed on 27th February 2022.

²¹ DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU, Annex I.

clean energy sources, primary energy factors of different carriers²² and the share of renewable energy sources in the entire grid make the building sector sustainable, energy-efficient and promote the target of achieving zero-energy consumption.

Photovoltaic (PV) has a colossal role to play. “The Climate Target Plan” shows wind and solar power supplying over 60% of EU electricity in 2050, up from about 13% in 2015²³. “International Energy Agency” (‘IEA’) speculates expansion of photovoltaic capacity instead by 2040²⁴. 1 kWh of electricity generation for self-consumption via a PV-battery system has a carbon footprint of about 80 g CO_{2eq}/kWh which is higher than the footprint of PV electricity consumed directly or fed into the grid, which is about 55 g CO_{2eq}/kWh²⁵. On the other hand, waste volumes are very low making it not economically feasible to treat end-of-life PV modules²⁶. To address several of these sustainability points, *Ecodesign*²⁷ and *Energy Labelling*²⁸ support the transition to ‘Circular Economy’ in product policy²⁹. As stipulated in *Point 1 of Directive 2009/125/EC, Directive 2005/32/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2005* was amended that set out the framework for ‘Ecodesign’ of the products³⁰. Harmonization of ‘Ecodesign’ requirements for all energy-related products (that includes products used in residential building affecting the energy performance of the building viz. windows, insulation materials, PV systems, water/heat-using products)³¹ can be done at the Union level³².

It is crucially important to identify that *Regulation (EU) 2017/1369 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2017* on setting framework for energy labelling, repealed *Directive 2010/30/EU* stating that the Directive has been a focal

²² DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU, Annex I.

²³ European Commission. *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 3/5*. Brussels: EU.p.98.

²⁴ *ibid* p.98.

²⁵ IEA PVPS Task 12 Report “Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Residential PV and Battery Storage Systems” (2020), ISBN 978-3-906042-97-8, p.9.

²⁶ European Commission. *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 3/5*. Brussels: EU.p.124.

²⁷ DIRECTIVE 2009/125/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for energy-related products, Article 1, p.14.

²⁸ REGULATION (EU) 2017/1369 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 July 2017 setting a framework for energy labelling and repealing Directive 2010/30/EU, Article 1, p.7.

²⁹ European Commission. *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 3/5*. Brussels: EU.p.124-125.

³⁰ DIRECTIVE 2009/125/EC (n 26)

³¹ DIRECTIVE 2009/125/EC, Point 4, p.1.

³² *ibid* Point 2, p.1.

legal instrument in the context of targets and gaining experience³³. It is, therefore, appropriate to legislate *Regulation (EU) 2017/1369* by amending the provisions on energy labelling and ecodesign from *Directive 2010/30/EU* (that were based on *Directive 2009/125/EC*) to enhance the scope and effectiveness of the Directive³⁴. *Regulation (EU) 2017/1369* takes into consideration the progress made so far over the decade and therefore, imposes clear and detailed rules prohibiting the different transpositions on energy-related products used in building stock by the Member States that came from *Directive 2010/30/EU*³⁵. Thus, leading to a course of rapid advancement as needed unanimously at the EU level to achieve more ambitious targets for the next decade.

Before interpreting the aspects of *Directive 2010/31/EU*, it is supportive to understand the competitiveness of heat pumps and other renewable energy sources for residential buildings. Heat pumps are used for space heating, domestic hot water as well as cooling in buildings. Residential heat pumps go up to 20 kW thermal for single-family use or multiple and include all ambient (air, solar, ground, water) and geothermal sources, hybrid heat pumps (natural gas) and reversible heat pumps³⁶. Heat pumps will play a major role in residential buildings with the rise in the share of decarbonised electricity and more electrification for district heating and cooling³⁷. The heat pump (HP) sector is already the largest contributor to the rise in renewable energy production for heating and cooling in the EU³⁸. The useable heat generation from heat pumps in the EU increased from 96 TWh in 2011 to 250 TWh in 2020, 12% growth per year as considered by European Heat Pump Association (EHPA)³⁹. The collective installed capacity of the wind energy sector (both onshore and offshore wind) in the EU increased by 123% from 80 GW in 2010 to 178.7 GW in 2020⁴⁰. Deployment of the offshore wind sector was even more distinguishable, soaring to 14.6 GW in 2020 from 1.6 GW in 2010⁴¹ and therefore increasing the

³³ REGULATION (EU) 2017/1369 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 July 2017 setting a framework for energy labelling and repealing Directive 2010/30/EU, Point 3, p.1.

³⁴ *ibid* Point 4, p. 4-5.

³⁵ *ibid* Point 6, p. 5.

³⁶ European Commission. *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 3/5*. Brussels: EU.p.127.

³⁷ COM (2020) 299 final. *Powering a climate-neutral economy: An EU Strategy for Energy System Integration*, p.8.

³⁸ European Commission. *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 3/5*. Brussels: EU.p.127

³⁹ European Commission. *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 3/5*. Brussels: EU.p.130.

⁴⁰ *ibid*.p.41.

⁴¹ *ibid* p.41.

share of decarbonised electricity in the grid, affecting the primary energy factor and thus overall energy performance of the building. By looking at the evidence and green technologies affecting the building sector, it essentially solidifies the application of provisions in and effectiveness of *Directive 2010/31/EU* as a focal legal tool.

Article 1 of *Directive 2010/31/EU* states the subject matter by taking into account the framework for calculating the integrated energy performance of buildings and building units, application of minimum energy performance requirements to new and existing buildings, need for national plans, energy certification, regular inspection of heating and cooling systems, control systems, all based on the outdoor, indoor and local climate requirements⁴². Accordingly, it identifies the key elements of the energy performance of a residential building and aligns with the target of energy consumption reduction. Given the long renovation cycle for existing buildings, the buildings have a long-term impact on energy consumption. In the same light, *Point 15* of *Directive 2010/31/EU* demands exploration of alternative energy supply systems to full measures and to ensure that needs of the cooling and heating demands are met to cost optimal-level. *Article 3b* of ‘TEU’ (1992 version)⁴³ or *Article 5* of ‘TEU’ (2012 version)⁴⁴, therefore, comes into the picture as stated in *Point 33* of *Directive 2010/31/EU* to widen the effectiveness of the objectives using the principle of subsidiarity⁴⁵. There is a clear distinction made by *Article 6*⁴⁶ and *Article 7*⁴⁷ of the Directive between the new and existing buildings for setting ‘minimum energy requirement’ in accordance with *Article 4*⁴⁸ since existing buildings undergo a prolonged period of renovation and need technical, economic and functionality feasibility. Consequently, *Article 5* of *Directive 2010/31/EU* identifies the energy balance calculations for buildings and lays a methodology framework for all the Member States stipulating cost-optimal levels⁴⁹. One of the

⁴² DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings, Article 1, p. 17-18.

⁴³ Treaty on European Union (92/C 191/01), 1992, Article 3b, p.6

⁴⁴ Consolidated version of Treaty on European Union, 2012, Article 5, p.18.

⁴⁵ DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings, Point 33, p.17.

⁴⁶ *ibid* Article 6, p.20.

⁴⁷ DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings, p.20-21.

⁴⁸ *ibid* Article 4, p.19-20.

⁴⁹ *ibid* Article 5, p.20.

most robust provisions outlines a fabric for financial support programmes in the view of standard and legal requirements between the national or regional authorities or bodies⁵⁰. This will catalyse the transition of building stock to nearly zero-energy consumption with the help of instruments that are most relevant to the Member States⁵¹. Buildings account for 40% of total energy consumption and for sustainable utilisation of energy supplies the Directive gives provisions on inspections of heating systems⁵², air-conditioning systems⁵³, issuance of energy certificates⁵⁴ and training for those responsible for implementing this Directive⁵⁵. The transposition of the Directive into laws, regulations, administrative provisions by the State Members was set as 9th July 2012⁵⁶.

Section 4. Case C-67/12, Failure of a Member State to fulfil obligations – Directive 2002/91/EC - Energy Performance of Buildings – Incomplete Transposition, European Commission v. Kingdom of Spain of 16 January 2014.

In Case C-67/12, the European Commission filed the case for judgement against the Kingdom of Spain stating that the Kingdom of Spain had failed to adopt all the laws, regulations and administrative procedures necessary for transposition of *Articles 3, 7 and 8 of Directive 2002/91/EC* of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2002 on energy performance of buildings and failed to notify the Commission within the set deadlines of those measures under the combined provisions of those articles and *Article 29 of Directive 2010/31/EU* of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings⁵⁷.

The Commission argued that *Royal Decree 1027/2007* of the Kingdom of Spain was an incomplete transposition of *Article 8(a) of Directive 2002/91* because it sets out measures for inspection of boilers after that decree had entered into force and left it to the local authorities to establish the schedule for boilers in existing buildings⁵⁸.

⁵⁰ DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings, Article 10, p.22.

⁵¹ *ibid* p.22.

⁵² *ibid* Article 14, p 24.

⁵³ *ibid* Article 15, p 25.

⁵⁴ *ibid* Article 12, p 23.

⁵⁵ *ibid* Article 20, p 26.

⁵⁶ *ibid* Article 28, p 27.

⁵⁷ Case C-67/12, the Commission v. Spain, paragraph 1, p.1-2.

⁵⁸ *ibid* paragraph 57, p. 9.

The Kingdom of Spain affirmed that it chose to transpose *Article 8 of Directive 2002/91* fully even though the Directive had set out two alternatives viz. *Article 8(a)* or *8(b)* as solutions⁵⁹. On the contrary, according to the Commission's findings, the Kingdom of Spain didn't choose the combined method for transposing *Article 8* of *Directive 2002/91* fully into national law, apparently, from Recital 8 in the preamble to *Royal Decree 1027/2007*, it became evident that the objective of the latter was to transpose *Article 8(a)* of that Directive alone⁶⁰. The Commission further pointed out in its reply of 22nd July 2010 of formal notice, that the Kingdom of Spain referred solely to rules of the respective local authorities – only some of which were processed although provisions intended to transpose *Article 8(b)* into Spanish Law were already in force on that date⁶¹. The Commission observed that *Technical Instruction 3.4.4* of *Royal Decree 1027/2007* was very vague and cannot be constituted as transposition for *Article 8(b)* of *Directive 2002/91* that set out measures for inspection of boilers⁶².

The Court found that the Kingdom of Spain failed to communicate the regulations necessary in respect of existing buildings and the transposition by the means of *Royal Decree 1027/2007* was true to the point where the rule entered into the force while measures for the regular inspection of the boilers in service before the decree entered into the force weren't considered⁶³. According to Directive 2002/91 the Member States after the adoption of all the measures should notify the Commission so that the Commission can verify whether the objectives were achieved or not as laid down in that Directive; the Kingdom of Spain failed in this event⁶⁴. The Court affirmed that the Kingdom of Spain had partly transposed *Article 8(a)* as well as *Article 8(b)* and didn't constitute a solution fully for only one provision out of the two alternatives which should have been the case as set by the Directive⁶⁵.

The complaint alleging a failure to transpose *Article 8* of *Directive 2002/91* concerning the existing buildings was, therefore, well-founded and under *Article*

⁵⁹ Case C-67/12, the Commission v. Spain, paragraph 58, p.9.

⁶⁰ *ibid* paragraph 59, p. 9.

⁶¹ *ibid* paragraph 59

⁶² *ibid* paragraph 60, p.10.

⁶³ *ibid* paragraph 65, p.10.

⁶⁴ *ibid* paragraph 70, p.11.

⁶⁵ *ibid* paragraph 71, p.11.

138(1) of the *Rules of Procedure of the Court of Justice*, the costs must be paid by the unsuccessful party as applicable⁶⁶.

Section 5. Evaluation of the legal framework and opinion on foreseeable legislative action.

The critical analysis of the directives, regulations, case law and other similar legal instruments (the Treaties) point to the fact that international, European, national and regional legal frameworks are effective and very well-defined. As identified, a directive helps to initiate the laws, regulations and administrative procedures relevant to a national legal framework. The experience gained through the provisions set in a directive over a given period enables the national legal frameworks to stipulate more effective national laws and regulations by narrowing down on a specific area of focus that needs to be addressed (often including Recommendations and Opinions). In that context, *Directive 2010/31/EU* (EPBD) turned out to be a pivotal legal tool to mould the measures for *Regulation (EU) 2017/1369* which legislated the rules on ecodesign requirements of energy-related products. The greatest need for legislative action in the foreseeable future, therefore, is in the area of permits. The directives need to bring in the provisions for catalysing the process of regulating permits. That will indeed result in direct regulations at the Union level which will harmonize different layers of permits for the Member States. That will indeed spur the projects reducing delays and thus the costs.

Section 6. Conclusion. More efforts needed for the existing building stock.

Buildings account for 40% of the final energy consumption and therefore are the central element for 2030 zero-energy targets. The Directive on the energy performance of the buildings is a crucial legal instrument along with other regulations that stem from it. Principles for nearly zero-energy buildings must become the base for new policies and approaches. The Member States should notify dutifully the Commission on the developments made in the new and existing building stock so that the Commission can verify if the objectives set in a directive need to be updated or not. Full implementation of existing energy legislation must always be a top priority.

⁶⁶ Case C-67/12, the Commission v. Spain, paragraph 77, p.11.

Abbreviations.

EPBD – Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.

EU – European Union.

EEC – European Economic Community Treaty.

EHPA – European Heat Pump Association.

GW – Gigawatt.

HP – Heat Pump.

IEA – International Energy Agency.

PV – Photovoltaic.

TEU – Treaty on the European Union.

TFEU – Treaty on the Fuctioning of the European Union.

TWh – Terawatt Hour.

UN – United Nations.

Bibliography.

Legal Acts:

1. Consolidated Version of the Treaty on The European Union, 2012. *Official Journal of the European Union*.
2. Consolidated Version of The Treaty On The Functioning Of The European Union ('TFEU'), 2020. *Official Journal of the European Union*.
3. Treaty on European Union (92/C 191/01), 1992. *Official Journal of the European Communities*.
4. DIRECTIVE 2009/125/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for energy-related products, 2009. *Official Journal of the European Union*.
5. DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings, 2010. *Official Journal of the European Union*.
6. REGULATION (EU) 2017/1369 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 4 July 2017 setting a framework for energy labelling and repealing Directive 2010/30/EU. (2017). 198/1 *Official Journal of the European Union*.

Case Law:

1. Case C-67/12; European Commission v. Kingdom of Spain. Court of Justice of the European Union. 16th January 2014.

EU Reports:

1. COM(2020) 299 final. *Powering a climate-neutral economy: An EU Strategy for Energy System Integration*. Brussels: European Commission.
2. *Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Residential PV and Battery Storage Systems* (2020). ISBN 978-3-906042-97-8. Paris: International Energy Agency.
3. European Commission. (2021). *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 2/5*. Brussels: EU.
4. European Commission. (2021). *SWD (2021) 307 Final, Part 3/5*. Brussels: EU.

Websites:

1. European Union. *Summaries of EU Legislation*. Retrieved from EUR-Lex: Access to European Union Law: [EUR-Lex - 114530 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#) Accessed on 25th February 2022.
2. Eurostat, European Union. *Energy Efficiency Statistics*. Retrieved from Eurostat: Statistics Explained: [Glossary: Eurostat - Statistics Explained \(europa.eu\)](#) Accessed on 27th February 2022.